

THE THING ABOUT AUSTEN

A Podcast on Jane Austen's World

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SERIES INFORMATION

Series Title	The Thing About Austen: A Podcast About Jane Austen's World
Creators	Zan Cammack and Dian Neu
Host	Zan Cammack
Host Affiliation	Utah Valley University
Host ORCID	0009-0009-1908-7488
Host	Diane Neu
Host ORCID	0009-0003-9915-2185
Launch Date	June 16, 2021
Episodes	116 episodes (as of March 2026)
Release Schedule	Monthly
Website	https://www.thethingaboutausten.com
RSS Feed	https://pinecast.com/feed/the-thing-about-austen
License	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)
Series DOI	10.5281/zenodo.19163252

ABOUT THE PODCAST

The Thing About Austen is a public-facing academic podcast dedicated to the historical and cultural contexts of Jane Austen's fiction. The series examines the people, objects, material culture, and social history that shape Austen's novels and her world.

Each episode approaches a specific topic – ranging from Regency-era domestic practices and botanical culture to questions of class, gender, and illegitimacy – through close reading, archival research, and engagement with current Austen scholarship. The podcast combines scholarly rigor with an accessible register, functioning simultaneously as a public humanities resource and a peer-recognized research output.

Episodes incorporate full transcripts, bibliographies with DOI-linked sources, and standardized metadata, making each episode fully citable within academic research infrastructures including ORCID, OpenAlex, DataCite, and Digital Measures.

SCHOLARLY RECOGNITION AND IMPACT

The Thing About Austen has received the following scholarly recognition:

- **Peer-reviewed citation:** Collins, Emma. "An Emerald Enigma: The Symbolic Value of Ireland in *Emma*." *Persuasions* 45, no. 1 (2023): 250–62.
- **Peer-reviewed citation:** Moss, Hannah, and Joe Bray, eds. *Edinburgh Companion to Jane Austen and the Arts*. Edinburgh University Press, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781399500425>
- **Conference presentation:** Hosts presented as podcast hosts at the Jane Austen Society of North America (JASNA) Annual General Meeting.
- **Keynote address:** Hosts delivered keynote address at AustenCon, Sydney, Australia.
- **Media coverage:** Featured in *The Guardian* and in the Audible Blog.

EPISODE TYPES

The series encompasses four primary episode formats, often in combination:

- **Solo episodes:** In-depth discussions between the two hosts on a specific historical, cultural, or literary topic drawn from Austen's world.
- **Guest interviews:** Conversations with Austen scholars, historians, and subject experts providing specialist perspectives on episode themes.
- **Close reading:** Episodes focused on specific passages, scenes, or textual features in Austen's novels, examined in scholarly detail.
- **Historical and cultural context:** Episodes situating Austen's fiction within the material, social, and cultural conditions of late Georgian and Regency England.

HOW TO CITE THIS PODCAST SERIES

Chicago: Cammack, Zan, and Diane Neu. *The Thing About Austen*. Podcast series. Utah Valley University, Department of English. Launched June 16, 2021. <https://www.thethingaboutausten.com>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19163252.

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